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Research Article

Therapeutic Effect of Rosemary and Its Active Constituent on Nervous System Disorders

Vaidehi Bhaladhare*, Sayali Ganjiwale, Sachin Dighade

Institute of Pharmacy and Research, Anjangaon Bari Road, Badnera-Amravati, Maharashtra.

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ABSTRACT

Rosmarinus officinalis is one such Mediterranean herb that has drawn a lot of interest for its potential therapeutic application for a number of nervous system illnesses. The extract of rosemary, which is rich in components including ursolic acid, carnosic acid and rosmarinic acid, has strong neuroprotective, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties. By modifying inflammatory pathways and lowering oxidative stress, these active principles shield neuron from oxidative damage. There is growing evidence that rosemary can improve memory, neuroplasticity, and cognitive skills while also helping to control neurodegenerative disorders like Parkinson's and Alzheimer's. It also shows potential in treating mood disorders like depression by providing neurochemical modulation that promotes mental well-being. Compared to traditional medications, rosemary has less side effects, making it a useful adjunctive treatment for neurological disorders and psychiatric conditions. Multidimensional benefits place it with a promising candidate for application in modern medicine in relation to neuroprotection, cognitive enhancement, and maintenance for nervous system health.

INTRODUCTION

A member of the Lamiaceae family, rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*) is indigenous to the Mediterranean region. The Latin terms Ros (dew) and marinus (sea) are the source of its name, which translates to "dew of the sea." Rosemary is prized for its culinary and therapeutic uses and is known for its fragrant, needle-like leaves and unique scent. It was recognized as the Herb of the Year by

the International Herb Association in 2001. The growth reaches 1–2.5 m in height, with quadrangular stems and small, dark-green needle-like leaves. Flowers are small, white or purplish-blue, bloom from June to August.

Botanical Description of Rosemary

- **Family:** Lamiaceae (Mint family)

*Corresponding Author: Vaidehi Bhaladhare

Address: Institute of Pharmacy and Research, Anjangaon Bari Road, Badnera-Amravati, Maharashtra.

Email ✉: Vaidehibhaladhare@gmail.com

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- **Growth Habit:** Shrubby, woody perennial herb; grows 1–1.5 m in height and spreads 1 m wide.
- **Leaves:** Needle-shaped, 2–4 cm long, aromatic, resembling pine needles.
- **Stems:** Erect, woody, reddish-brown aging to grey; young stems are green and soft.
- **Flowers:** Small, pale blue to white in clusters on short spikes; attract bees for pollination.
- **Roots:** Fibrous, adapted to well-drained, rocky Mediterranean soils.
- **Growth Conditions:** Prefers sandy or loamy soils with full sun; drought-hardy and tolerates poor soils.

Other Names

Spanish: Romero

Portuguese: Alecrim

French/German: Rosmarin

Italian: Rosmarino

Uses of Rosemary

Rosemary is widely utilized for culinary, medicinal, cosmetic, and domestic applications. A flavouring agent, particularly in Mediterranean cuisine, meats, vegetables, and herbal teas, is one of its culinary applications. It works well to preserve food because of its antibacterial qualities. In terms of medicine, rosemary helps with digestion, improves memory and focus, and has anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and analgesic properties. Rosemary oil is used in aromatherapy to elevate mood, reduce stress, and increase mental clarity. It is also used in massages and baths to promote relaxation and ease tense muscles. In terms of appearance, rosemary extract improves skin health, lessens acne, and encourages healthy hair and a healthy scalp. Household applications include its use as a natural cleaning agent and insect repellent due to its antibacterial and fragrant characteristics.

Phytochemicals of Rosemary

Rosemary is rich in phytochemicals, including terpenoids, essential oils, alkaloids, and

flavonoids. Key compounds include caffeic acid, carnosic acid, chlorogenic acid, monomeric acid, oleanolic acid, rosmarinic acid, ursolic acid, alpha-pinene, camphor, carnosol, eucalyptol, rosmadial, rosmanol, rosmaquinones A and B, secohinokio, and derivatives of eugenol and luteolin.

1] Caffeic acid

A strong antioxidant, caffeine stabilizes free radicals, neutralizes them, lowers oxidative stress, and guards against cellular damage. In addition, it suppresses inflammation linked to neurological diseases including Alzheimer's and multiple sclerosis by blocking pro-inflammatory pathways like NF- κ B, lowering inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6) and COX-2 activity. The stimulation of antioxidants (SOD, glutathione peroxidase) and the control of MAPK pathways exert neuroprotective effects by increasing neuronal survival and decreasing apoptosis. Potential for Therapy: Because of its neuroprotective, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant qualities, caffeine is useful in the treatment of neurodegenerative illnesses like Parkinson's and Alzheimer's. By strengthening cellular antioxidant defence, it also provides antidepressant effects and protection against ischemic brain injury.

2] Carnosic Acid and Carnosol

Redox-sensitive antioxidant activity is exhibited by carnosic acid and carnosol, which target cells with elevated ROS levels while preserving healthy cells. By scavenging ROS, triggering the Nrf2 pathway, and increasing antioxidant enzymes like glutathione peroxidase and superoxide dismutase, they shield neurons from oxidative stress. These substances delay the progression of Alzheimer's disease by reducing neuroinflammation by lowering pro-inflammatory cytokines and preventing amyloid-beta aggregation. In Alzheimer's patients, carnosic acid also improves acetylcholine levels and cognitive performance by acting as an AChE inhibitor.

Therapeutic Potential: Carnosic acid and carnosol provide neuroprotective properties for the treatment of neurodegenerative illnesses including Parkinson's and Alzheimer's by lowering oxidative stress and neuroinflammation.

3] Rosmarinic Acid

By neutralizing reactive oxygen and nitrogen species, rosmarinic acid improves antioxidant enzymes (catalase, glutathione peroxidase, and SOD) and maintains the integrity of neural cells. By blocking the COX and LOX enzymes, it lowers cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6) and inflammation through the NF- κ B pathway. It keeps calcium levels stable to avoid excitotoxicity, inhibits amyloid-beta aggregation, and modifies the MAPK pathway to save neuronal cells. Its immune-modulatory properties minimize inflammation while boosting immunity by balancing cytokines and lowering histamine production. Because it is an MAO inhibitor, it raises dopamine and serotonin, which elevates mood, reduces anxiety, and relaxes the nervous system.

Therapeutic Uses: Neuroinflammation, autoimmune illnesses, and inflammatory conditions

like psoriasis can all be effectively treated with rosmarinic acid due to its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and neuroprotective qualities.

4] Ursolic acid

By scavenging ROS (reactive oxygen species) and boosting antioxidant enzymes, ursolic acid lessens oxidative cell damage. By blocking the NF- κ B pathway, COX, and LOX enzymes, as well as restoring normal nitric oxide levels, it reduces inflammation. It supports cognitive performance in neuroprotection by lowering oxidative stress, preventing neuroinflammation, and preserving acetylcholine levels. By triggering apoptosis and preventing tumor growth, it also possesses anticancer qualities. By activating AMPK, improving fatty acid oxidation, and decreasing fat

storage, ursolic acid also supports metabolic health and has anti-obesity and anti-diabetic properties.

Therapeutic Potential: Ursolic acid has the potential to treat oxidative stress, cancer, neurological diseases, chronic inflammation, and metabolic diseases like diabetes and obesity.

5] 1,8-Cineole (Eucalyptol)

1,8-Cineole has several therapeutic advantages, especially for neurological and pulmonary conditions. It protects lipids, proteins, and DNA by scavenging free radicals, acting as an antioxidant. The substance has potent anti-inflammatory properties that help with diseases including asthma and chronic bronchitis by regulating the NF- κ B pathway and blocking pro-inflammatory mediators (TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6). It also has soothing effects on the central nervous system and neuroprotective qualities, lowering oxidative and inflammatory damage to neurons. Additionally, it functions as a mucolytic agent, which is advantageous in respiratory disorders since it thins mucus and increases ventilation. Therapeutic Potential: 1,8-Cineole has anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties that protect the brain and prevent neurodegeneration. It is also useful for respiratory therapy, lowering mucus in bronchitis and asthma. Additionally, it has relaxing benefits, helping alleviate anxiety and enhancing mental clarity.

6] Camphor

Through its binding to TRP channels (TRPV1, TRPA1), camphor desensitizes sensory nerves, hence lowering inflammation and pain perception. By activating cold receptors in the nasopharynx, it also acts as a decongestant, enhancing airflow and reducing respiratory discomfort. It works well against viruses, fungi, and bacteria because of its antibacterial qualities, which target microbial membranes. Camphor improves circulation and cognitive function by stimulating the central nervous system.

Therapeutic Uses: Camphor is an anti-inflammatory and external analgesic. It helps with various types of arthritis disorders since it is administered externally and has a warming effect on the skin that improves local blood circulation, reducing muscle discomfort and stiffness. Additionally, camphor has antibacterial properties that make it beneficial for a variety of small wounds and skin irritation conditions.

7] α -Pinene

Through a variety of processes, α -pinene, the main component of rosemary, has medicinal effects. Because it has anti-inflammatory properties, α -pinene suppresses pro-inflammatory pathways. By precisely blocking the NF- κ B pathway, it was found to have an anti-inflammatory effect by lowering the levels of cytokines like TNF- α and IL-6, which are the main cause of inflammation. Additionally, its antioxidant activity prevents damage to cellular structures, particularly neurons, by scavenging ROS and lowering oxidative stress. In respiratory health, α -pinene is a bronchodilator, which relaxes the bronchial muscles, reducing airflow and, consequently, asthmatic symptoms. By blocking the enzyme acetylcholinesterase, which degrades acetylcholine, α -pinene has a neuroprotective effect that supports cognitive processes including memory and learning. Because of these pathways, α -pinene is beneficial for use in inflammatory, respiratory, and neuroprotective applications.

Therapeutic Effects: Use in Therapy Asthma and other respiratory conditions can be lessened with the help of α -pinene, a monoterpene with bronchodilator and anti-inflammatory qualities. Additionally, α -Pinene exhibits neuroprotective properties and cognitive advantages, enhancing memory and attentiveness.

8] Rosmanol

One polyphenolic that can be derived from rosemary is rosmannol, which primarily acts as an anti-inflammatory and antioxidant. In addition to

limiting oxidative stress and scavenging free radicals, it also suppresses pro-inflammatory pathways like NF- κ B and COX-2. Furthermore, rosmannol stimulates the production of antioxidant proteins, controls enzymatic activity such as acetylcholinesterase (AChE), which enhances cognitive function, and shields neurons from death. These actions may be indicative of rosmannol's neuroprotective and therapeutic properties, particularly in neurodegenerative conditions.

Effects of therapy: The primary benefits of rosmannol are its neuroprotective, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant qualities. Reduction of oxidative stress, inflammation, and neuronal damage, as well as improvement of cognitive function and defense against cellular damage, are examples of therapeutic outcomes in neurodegenerative illnesses.

9] Oleanolic acid

The oleanolic acid found in rosemary works in a number of ways, including reducing inflammation by blocking the NF- κ B pathway, protecting against oxidative stress by activating the Nrf2 antioxidant pathway, promoting liver health by regulating liver enzymes, inducing apoptosis in cancer cells by modulating apoptotic proteins, and inhibiting tumor growth via the PI3K/Akt pathway; regulating lipid metabolism by lowering cholesterol levels and improving lipid profiles. These actions all contribute to the therapeutic effects of rosemary. **Anti-inflammatory:** it blocks the inflammation phenomenon by reducing pro-inflammatory cytokines. Therefore, an antioxidant works in defensive mechanisms that protect cells from oxidative damage, either by scavenging free radicals or other antioxidant defense. **Hepatoprotective:** lowers the risk of damage to liver tissues and maintains the health of the liver. **Anti-cancerous:** They induce the death of cancerous cells, known as apoptosis, and limit tumour growth. **Lipid regulation:** It reduces

cholesterol and lipid deposition, thus helping to improve the functions of heart.

EFFECTS OF ROSEMARY CONSTITUENTS ON NERVOUS SYSTEM DISORDERS

A] Alzheimer disease

The primary cause of Alzheimer's disease is oxidative stress, which also contributes significantly to the formation of free radicals, mitochondrial malfunction, cell death, amyloid beta peptide deposition, and interaction with the mitochondrion. Alzheimer's disease is a complicated illness with a combination of environmental and genetic risk factors. Alzheimer's disease is characterized by a number of alterations in the brain, such as tau tangles, amyloid plaques, death of neurons, and loss of connections between neurons. Oxidative and nitrosative stress, which destroys neurons, is one way the condition may worsen. This is because amyloid- β causes reactive oxygen and nitrogen species to be produced. The Keap1/Nrf2 pathway, one of the body's most crucial natural defense mechanisms, fights oxidative stress and inflammation by inducing protection proteins and antioxidants. It can be seen as one potential target of treatment for all neurodegenerative diseases. The protective pathway under oxidative stress was found to be activated by a compound known as carnosic acid, thus showing an increase in antioxidant production in animals and lab studies. Carnosic acid's effects on amyloid- β -exposed brain cells in laboratory and animal models. According to the findings, a nasal dosage of 10 mg of carnosic acid per kilogram of body weight improved neuron health markers, lowered amyloid plaques, decreased signals of inflammation, and decreased tau protein accumulation in the hippocampus, which is a key location for this condition. Given that the FDA has determined that carnosic acid is safe for human consumption.

B] Memory and learning

It has been shown that rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*) can improve cognitive capacities, particularly memory and learning. Recent research is starting to show evidence that could back up the claims made about its traditional use: this plant may have an impact on cognitive function through a variety of methods. Since rosemary inhibits acetylcholinesterase, it is known to enhance neurotransmitter function by preventing the breakdown of acetylcholine, a neurotransmitter that is crucial for memory and learning. Because acetylcholine plays a crucial role in signal transmission between neurons, especially in areas of the brain that control memory formation, higher levels of this neurotransmitter have been linked to improved cognitive functioning. Cognitive Enhancement: The scents of rosemary can increase blood flow to the brain and oxygenation, improving concentration, memorization, and mental clarity. This includes antioxidant effects: strong antioxidants found in rosemary, such as carnosic acid and rosmarinic acid, help prevent oxidative stress and safeguard brain cells, which in turn helps to ensure memory and learning. Compounds like ursolic acid may reduce residual neuroinflammation by maintaining the environment surrounding healthy neurons, which are critical for memory and learning. Mood modulation: Rosemary's mild anxiolytic properties may ease stress and anxiety, resulting in a calm state that improves cognitive performance.

C] Depression

Rosmarinic acid and carnosic acid, two potent antioxidants, are found in rosemary. Antioxidants like these aid in reducing oxidative stress in the brain, which is frequently linked to mood disorders like depression. Among the severe chronic psychiatric diseases is depression. Numerous changes in the central nervous system's neuronal noradrenergic and serotonergic activity have been demonstrated by clinical and experimental studies. It has been shown to alter the gut microbiome and

reduce inflammatory markers linked to mental disorders, including TNF- α and IL-1 β . Such data would suggest that these extracts may be able to bring the gut-brain axis back to equilibrium. These are relatively new pathways that have gained interest recently in the treatment of depression and mood regulation. The findings of this study may therefore indicate that rosemary has a therapeutic effect on depressive-like behavior by increasing healthy gut flora and reducing the generation of inflammatory cytokines in the brain and nervous system. Relief of Mood and Anxiety According to clinical research, rosemary can enhance mood, memory, and sleep quality while lowering anxiety and despair. Using rosemary essential oil in aromatherapy has been shown to lower anxiety, increase alertness, and alleviate mood disorders brought on by stress. Activity of Antidepressants Rosemary's ursolic acid interacts with dopamine receptors (D1, D2), where it has been demonstrated to have an antidepressant effect that is boosted by dopamine-related medications but counteracted by antagonists.

D] Epilepsy

A disorder of the central nervous system, epilepsy causes learning and memory impairments as well as sporadic spontaneous convulsions. Because glutamate receptors are overactivated, it causes neuronal death. Although glutamate plays a role in cognitive processes including memory and learning as well as synaptic plasticity, it causes CNS neurodegeneration when its receptor is overactivated and at a greater concentration. Effects of Antioxidants on Neuroprotection: Antioxidants found in rosemary, such as rosmarinic and carnosic acids, lower oxidative stress, shielding neurons from harm during seizures and averting long-term alterations in the neurodegenerative profiles linked to epilepsy. These antioxidants prevent oxidative damage, maintain cell membranes, and prevent neurons from dying. Rosemary compounds, including

ursolic acid, rosmarinic acid, and carnosol, have demonstrated anti-inflammatory benefits in epilepsy by down-regulating pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β) and inhibiting enzymes like COX-2. This reduces the blood-brain barrier's vulnerability to seizures and protects neurons from inflammatory assaults, preserving their integrity. Modulation of neurotransmitters: The chemicals in rosemary, like carnosic acid and 1,8-cineole, activate GABA receptors, which lessens the excessive firing of neurons during seizures. Additionally, rosemary extract may influence serotonin and dopamine levels, which would relax the nervous system. Calcium and Sodium Channel Modulation: When calcium and sodium channels aren't working properly, neurons become more excitable, which is followed by status epilepticus. The seizure activity may be eliminated by rosemary's modulation of these channels.

E] Parkinson's disease (PD)

Shaking hands, delayed movement, rigidity, and postural instability are some of the symptoms of Parkinson's disease (PD), a chronic neurological illness brought on by the loss of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra. The high oxygen consumption and polyunsaturated fatty acid concentration of the substantia nigra make oxidative stress, a major contributor to neuronal death, especially harmful there. Through reactive oxygen species (ROS), inflammation, mitochondrial malfunction, and apoptosis, this oxidative stress causes neuronal degeneration. Recent research has shown that the rosemary chemicals carnosol and carnosic acid can protect dopaminergic neurons from oxidative damage brought on by Parkinson's disease. In mouse models, carnosol demonstrated neuroprotective effects by increasing tyrosine hydroxylase, an enzyme necessary for the synthesis of dopamine. Through its anti-oxidant properties, carnosic acid protects dopaminergic neurons by regulating

oxidative stress and apoptotic pathways. Other antioxidant enzymes that are essential for preventing oxidative damage, like SOD and catalase, were also activated. By lowering oxidative damage, increasing dopaminergic neuron survival, and delaying the course of the disease, both substances show significant therapeutic potential for Parkinson's disease. However, more clinical research is required to validate their efficacy.

F] Neuropathic pain

Anti-inflammatory Activity: By inhibiting pro-inflammatory enzymes (COX-2, LOX, TNF- α , and IL-1 β), rosemary's components, including rosmarinic acid and carnosol, have anti-inflammatory qualities that help reduce neuropathic pain.

Antioxidant Activity: By reducing oxidative stress and delaying the degeneration of nerves, they also function as antioxidants to balance free radicals, which may help to reduce pain feelings.

Pain Pathway Modulation: To reduce pain signals, compounds in rosemary increase GABA activity and modulate opioid receptors. They use opioid pathways and GABA receptors to control neuropathic pain.

Neuroprotective Effect: Carnosol and carnosic acid may prevent nerve degeneration, which is a contributing factor to neuropathic pain, by activating neurotrophic factors and improving neuron survival and function.

Actions of Carnosic Acid: Prevents oxidative and inflammatory damage to neurons. increases dopaminergic neurons' survival (related to Parkinson's disease).

Mechanisms: Increases the expression of antioxidant enzymes like glutathione peroxidase by activating the Nrf2/ARE pathway. suppresses cytokines that promote inflammation, including IL-1 β and TNF- α . **Neurotransmitters Blockers of neurotransmitters:** Some of rosemary's active ingredients include antagonistic qualities that block NMDA pain receptors, reducing nervous

system hyperexcitability and pain transduction thus could treat neuropathic pain.

CONCLUSION

This review has demonstrated that the bioactive chemicals found in rosemary, such as rosmarinic acid, carnosic acid, rosmarinol, and others, have significant therapeutic promise in the treatment of illnesses of the neurological system. These substances have shown a broad range of pharmacological actions. Most intriguing is their powerful antioxidant potential, which can be used to combat reactive oxygen species and undoubtedly lower oxidative stress levels, which are thought to be a key cause of neurodegenerative illnesses. These substances' anti-inflammatory properties have consequences for the pathways linked to COX-2 and NF-kB, two of the pathways linked to neuroinflammation. Additionally, rosemary's components promoted synaptic plasticity and shielded neurons from apoptosis, which enhanced cognition by controlling enzymes such as acetylcholinesterase and an augmentation of neurotransmitter levels.

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